

Supplementary Material

for the manuscript

Insights into the Arabia–Anatolia plate boundary from integrated SAR analysis and detailed modelling of the 2023 Türkiye–Syria earthquakes

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SUPPLEMENTARY TEXT

This Supplement provides additional material supporting the satellite-derived deformation analysis and the InSAR modelling. It includes displacement results of the Sentinel-1, ALOS-2 and SAOCOM-1 SAR datasets, the sampling strategies for the inversion; the construction of the uniform-slip and distributed-slip inversion models; the final geometric and kinematic parameters of the optimised fault model; and diagnostics of slip uncertainty and model resolution.

Static stress-change maps derived directly from the final slip distribution are also included. These maps depict elastic shear-stress variations on the fault planes, computed following Ripperger and Mai (2004), and are best viewed as a spatial representation of slip gradients (first derivatives). No Coulomb Failure Stress analysis is undertaken.

Modelling procedure

The modelling process followed has two steps. The first one is the estimation of the uniform slip solution by performing a non-linear inversion. The non-linear inversion optimization employs the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm (Levenberg 1944; Marquardt 1963) and is executed with multiple random initializations to reduce the likelihood of the least-squares cost function becoming trapped in local minimum. During non-linear inversion, the goal is to minimise the weighted mean sum of the squares of the errors between observed and modelled data. The cost function Φ is:

$$\Phi = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i^N \frac{(d_{i,obs} - d_{i,mod})^2}{\sigma_i}$$

where $d_{i,obs}$ and $d_{i,mod}$ are the observed and modelled displacements of the i -th data point and σ_i its standard deviation.

For the uncertainty estimation, an empirical approach is applied. At first the data variance/covariance matrix is constructed. To this end the autocorrelation function of

noise-only portion of the interferogram was analysed and then, after the estimation of the variance/covariance matrix, synthetic realistic noise datasets are generated and added to the observed interferograms. After that, a non-linear inversion is performed again to get a new set of inverted parameters. Starting this time from the optimum parameter configuration. This inversion of observed+noise data is repeated several times, each time adding a different noise contribution, to find the uncertainty affecting the inverted parameters.

In this study, given the complexity of the displacement pattern, the non-linear inversion must be carried out over a number of fault segments, identified on the fault trace based on the DInSAR results.

When it comes to the input data for this specific event, the initial attempt was to use each dataset as a whole (Figure S3). We performed the first round of non-linear inversions assuming at the beginning simplified models with only few segments (initially 4 segments). This was to try to model the broad observed displacement and also to understand better how to handle the input data. At this first stage the inversions performed were non-linear in an attempt to firstly identify the main kinematic characteristics.

Gradually, we started making the model more complex by adding segments to realize that to achieve a high detail model and at the same time to have a convergence, we had to separate spatially each of the input datasets into smaller areas. Thus, in this second round of non-linear inversions we attempted to model the areas of the N segments and the S segments separately. Many inversion tests were performed (taking also into account external data like the seismicity), however, again this was not allowing a smooth inversion process. For this reason, we proceeded with a third round of non-linear inversions that were even more in number than those of the previous ones. The main concept was to isolate multiple areas on the fault and work on them separately (e.g. Figure S4, and Figure 10) having as a goal to build-up, segment-by-segment, the whole multi-segment uniform slip model.

When the deformation field is particularly complex due to the presence of several segments, an alternative approach to the simultaneous inversion of all segments can be used, in order to eliminate possible cross-tradeoffs between different segments. The contribution of a previously constrained segment is subtracted from the observed data, and then the inversion of the residual is performed to constrain the parameters of the segment under analysis. The inversion software is designed to make this approach user-friendly, allowing the possibility to include segments that contribute to the displacement field as “fixed sources,” without parameters to invert, together with those that are to be inverted. This flexibility is available for both non-linear and linear inversion.

In each area, therefore, once the optimum uniform slip was found, we were moving to the neighbouring one inverting for a new segment; however, each time keeping as a fixed deformation source the segment from the previous inversion.

During this procedure we sometimes had to go back and make additional revisions to a previous uniform slip model, in order to further fine-tune it in an iterative-like approach. The uniform-slip solutions are shown in Figure S5.

As already mentioned in the maintext, SAOCOM-1 data had an important contribution in the modelling. They allowed us to define the fault trace in detail, the data coverage was rich, and also offered on-fault information. Of course, these all had a clear contribution in the inversion procedure. Below in Figure S6 we show an example of two inversion results for the segments N1 and N2, without and with SAOCOM-1 POT range and azimuth datasets. In the latter inversion, the uncertainties are decreased.

In the linear inversion, the relation of the model parameters (the slip values of the fault patches) with the observed data can be expressed analytically with the following linear system of equations:

$$\begin{bmatrix} d_{\text{obs}} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} G \\ \varepsilon \nabla^2 \end{bmatrix} m$$

where d_{obs} are the observed data, G are the Green's functions and \mathbf{m} are the parameters to be found (unknowns), ∇^2 is a Laplacian operator and ϵ is the damping factor.

During the linear inversions, the same segment-by-segment modelling procedure was followed, by keeping in each case fixed all the previously finished best linear inversion models. Finally, an additional set of inversions was performed; after having defined all the slip distribution models, we went again back and redid the non-linear inversion of a few of the segments in order to improve them. An example is mentioned for the case of the S1 segment, where we performed another non-linear inversion having fixed all the other slip distribution sources. After the re-definition of the uniform slip model, we then proceeded to the re-estimation of its slip distribution model. Thus, based on the above strategy, we created the final slip model for the 2023 earthquake events (Figure S7). As demonstrated in Figure S8, the strikes differences between neighbouring segments are higher than their uncertainty, thereby offering a quantitative justification for our proposed segmentation.

Static stress Change on the fault plane

The occurrence of an earthquake redistributes shear stress along the fault plane according to the spatial pattern of slip. Static stress changes were computed directly from the final slip model using the methodology of Ripperger and Mai (2004), based on the stochastic fault framework of Andrews (1980). In the wavenumber domain, the static shear-stress change $\tau(kx, kz)$ is related to the slip $D(kx, kz)$ via $\tau(kx, kz) = K(kx, kz) \cdot D(kx, kz)$, where K is the static stiffness kernel (Ripperger & Mai, 2004).

The slip distribution is first transformed into the 2-D wavenumber domain, where the elastic relationship between slip and stress is expressed through a static stiffness function. Applying this stiffness function and transforming back into the spatial domain yields maps of stress change on the fault surface. For the two February 6 events, the modelled rake angles indicate predominantly left-lateral strike-slip motion on all segments, so slip was treated as purely strike-slip for the stress computation. The shear modulus μ was taken as 3.3×10^{10} N/m², representative of upper-crustal rocks.

Figure S12 shows the resulting static shear-stress changes for each segment of the southern rupture (Mw 7.8; segments S1–S14) and the northern rupture (Mw 7.5; segments N1–N8). Positive changes (red) correspond to stress drops in areas of significant slip, while negative changes (blue) mark stress increases in low-slip or unruptured areas. Because these stress values are derived directly from the spatial gradients of the final slip model, the patterns closely follow the slip distribution.

Detailed segment-by-segment stress values are reported in Table S2, including maxima of ~ 126 MPa and ~ 150 MPa for the southern and northern ruptures, respectively. These large values partly reflect the patch-scale slip roughness and the high spatial resolution of the model, and they should not be interpreted as representative average stress drops over entire fault segments. The calculations focus exclusively on on-fault shear-stress changes; off-fault stress variations in the surrounding crust are not considered. These values should therefore not be interpreted as representative stress drops of the entire fault segment but rather as local indicators of slip-gradient intensity.

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURES

Figure S1. DInSAR results retrieved by processing the Sentinel-1 data acquired from ascending and descending orbits, respectively. The interferogram shown in (a) is obtained by merging the DInSAR results of the two exploited ascending tracks T14 and T116, respectively, whereas in (b) the presented results are obtained through the descending data relevant to the track T21. These products were generated through the EPOSAR tool (Monterroso et al. 2019, Monterroso et al. 2020, Monterroso et al. 2022) and are available via the EPOSAR TCS catalogue (<https://www.ics-c.epos-eu.org>).

Figure S2. DInSAR wrapped interferometric results retrieved by processing the ALOS-2 data acquired from descending (left) ascending (right) orbits. There is improved coherence across much of the deformation field, compared to the DInSAR Sentinel-1 maps.

Figure S3. Example of the initial sampling used in early non-linear inversion tests.

Figure S4. Example of sampling performed to focus on the easternmost end of the S segments.

Figure S5. Results of the non-linear inversions for the uniform-slip sources. Each coloured rectangle represents a fault segment whose parameters were obtained from the multi-step non-linear inversion procedure.

Modelling only ALOS-2 +SENTINEL-1	Modelling ALOS-2 +SENTINEL-1 + SAOCOM-1
<p><i>Input datasets:</i> ALOS2_20220905_20230220_Asc_LOS ALOS2_20220916_20230217_Desc_LOS Sentinel1_20230204_20230228_Asc_Range Sentinel1_20230128_20230209_Asc_Range Sentinel1_20230129_20230210_Desc_Range</p>	<p><i>Input datasets:</i> ALOS2_20220905_20230220_Asc_LOS ALOS2_20220916_20230217_Desc_LOS SAOCOM1_20220502_20230414_Asc_Azimuth SAOCOM1_20220502_20230214_Asc_Range SAOCOM1_120220614_20230225_Asc_Azimuth SAOCOM1_20220614_20230225_Asc_Range SAOCOM1_20220721_20230214_Asc_Azimuth SAOCOM1_20220721_20230214_Asc_Range SAOCOM1_20220427_20230422_Asc_Range SAOCOM1_20220529_20230420_Asc_Azimuth SAOCOM1_20220529_20230430_Asc_Range SAOCOM1_20220630_20230225_Asc_Range SAOCOM1_20220630_20230225_Asc_Range Sentinel1_20230204_20230228_Asc_Range Sentinel1_20230128_20230209_Asc_Range Sentinel1_20230129_20230210_Desc_Range SAOCOM1_20220427_20230422_Asc_Azimuth</p>
<i>Modelling Results</i>	<i>Modelling Results</i>
<p>N1 segment:</p> <p>Length: 50000.0 m, fixed Width: 13467.9 m, (sigma 498.3) Depth: -434.3 m, (sigma 45.7) Dip: 90 deg, fixed Strike: 240.05 deg, (sigma 0.13) East: 37.755256 deg, (sigma 0.002255) North: 38.041134 deg, (sigma 0.000985) Rake: -15.80 deg, (sigma 0.38)</p> <p>N2 segment:</p> <p>Length: 50000.0 m, fixed Width: 15327.2 m, (sigma 224.2) Depth: -1113.5 m, (sigma 14.5) Dip: 73.97 deg, (sigma 0.27) Strike: 281.38 deg, (sigma 0.05) East: 37.229103 deg, (sigma 0.000832) North: 38.024222 deg, (sigma 0.000136) Rake: -2.41 deg, (sigma 0.27)</p>	<p>N1 segment:</p> <p>Length: 50000.0 m, fixed Width: 10531.0 m, (sigma 227.9) Depth: -1212.4 m, (sigma 35.9) Dip: 50.07 deg, (sigma 0.64) Strike: 230.29 deg, (sigma 0.06) East: 37.819715 deg, (sigma 0.000894) North: 38.081270 deg, (sigma 0.000528) Rake: -10.00 deg, (sigma 0.30)</p> <p>N2 segment:</p> <p>Length: 50000.0 m, fixed Width: 15535.3 m, (sigma 135.0) Depth: -1316.7 m, (sigma 5.6) Dip: 59.84 deg, (sigma 0.20) Strike: 281.67 deg, (sigma 0.04) East: 37.215692 deg, (sigma 0.000600) North: 38.029841 deg, (sigma 0.000117) Rake: -2.49 deg, (sigma 0.16)</p>

Figure S6. Comparison between inversion results for N1 and N2 segments, having as input only the Sentinel-1 POT range and ALOS-2 LOS DInSAR data (left) and after

adding to these also the SAOCOM-1 POT range and azimuth datasets (right). Incorporating SAOCOM-1 data reduces the uncertainties.

Figure S7. Slip distribution model of the February 2023 Türkiye-Syria events. Colour scale indicates slip amplitude (in meters).

Figure S8. Segment strikes and their formal uncertainties of the non-linear inversion. Differences in strike between neighbouring segments exceed the associated uncertainties, supporting the proposed segmentation.

Figure S9. Comparison between Observed and Modeled InSAR displacements.

Figure S10. Slip uncertainties for all segments, derived from the model covariance matrix.

Figure S11. Resolution of the slip distribution model, expressed as the diagonal of the model resolution matrix (Menke, 1989). Values close to 1 indicate nearly perfectly resolved patches, typically near the surface and within areas of dense SAR coverage.

Figure S12. Static shear-stress changes on the fault planes computed from the final slip distribution using the elastic spectral formulation of Ripperger and Mai (2004). Lower panels correspond to the first Mw 7.8 rupture (southern system; segments S1–S14), and upper panels correspond to the second Mw 7.5 rupture (northern system; segments N1–N8). Positive values (red) indicate local stress drops associated with strong slip gradients, whereas negative values (blue) represent stress increases in low-slip or unruptured areas. These values reflect patch-scale slip derivatives and should be interpreted as qualitative indicators of on-fault stress redistribution rather than as absolute estimates of physical stress drop.

References (supplementary material)

Andrews, D. J. (1980). A stochastic fault model: I. Static case. *J. Geophys. Res. Solid Earth* 85, 3867–3877. doi:10.1029/JB085iB07p03867

Levenberg, K. (1944). A method for the solution of certain non-linear problems in least squares. *Q. Appl. Math.* 2, 164–168.

Menke, W. (1989). *Geophysical Data Analysis: Discrete Inverse Theory*. San Diego: Academic Press, 289 pp.

Monterroso, F., Bonano, M., De Luca, C., De Novellis, V., Lanari, R., Manunta, M., et al. (2019). Unsupervised and automatic generation of DInSAR coseismic displacement maps by means of Sentinel-1 data. In: *IGARSS 2019 – IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium*, Yokohama, 9658–9661. doi:10.1109/IGARSS.2019.8898772

Monterroso, F., Bonano, M., De Luca, C., Lanari, R., Manunta, M., Manzo, M., et al. (2020). A global archive of coseismic DInSAR products obtained through unsupervised Sentinel-1 data processing. *Remote Sens.* 12, 3189. doi:10.3390/rs12193189

Monterroso, F., De Luca, C., Zinno, I., Manunta, M., and Casu, F. (2022). Automatic generation of Sentinel-1 DInSAR co-seismic maps at global scale. In: *2022 IEEE 21st Mediterranean Electrotechnical Conference (MELECON)*, Palermo, 460–463. doi:10.1109/MELECON53508.2022.9843041

Okada, Y. (1985). Surface deformation due to shear and tensile faults in a half-space. *Bull. Seismol. Soc. Am.* 75, 1135–1154.

Ripperger, J., and Mai, P. M. (2004). Fast computation of static stress changes on 2D faults from final slip distributions. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 31, L18610. doi:10.1029/2004GL020594

SUPPLEMENTARY TABLES
Table S1. Model parameters and uncertainties.

Segment	Strike °	Dip°	Rake°
S1	230.09 (± 18.25)	78.27 (± 15.06)	2.77 (± 1.86)
S2	262.47 (± 0.04)	78 (± 0.01)	5.42 (± 0.15)
S3*	52.99	80.12	-5
S4	67.06 (± 0.05)	80.12 (± 0.5)	-5.68 (± 0.28)
S5	83.21 (± 0.18)	82.02 (± 1.03)	-22.07 (± 0.37)
S6	50.63 (± 0.05)	72.12 (± 0.41)	2.8 (± 0.27)
S7*	235.52	89	18
S8	240.04 (± 1.38)	64.6 (± 1.84)	18.7 (± 1.95)
S9	254 (± 0.13)	63 (± 1.93)	-3.8 (± 0.58)
S10	216.09 (± 0.25)	90	-7.52 (± 0.74)
S11	239.62 (± 0.18)	85.33 (± 0.61)	2.46 (± 0.25)
S12	43.95 (± 0.13)	74.76 (± 0.42)	-5 (± 0.57)
S13	29.93 (± 0.13)	74.76 (± 0.42)	-5 (± 0.57)
S14	21.76 (± 0.06)	89.46 (± 0.28)	-4.17 (± 0.39)

N1	230.29 (± 0.06)	50.07 (± 0.64)	-10 (± 0.3)
N2	281.67 (± 0.04)	59.84 (± 0.2)	-2.49 (± 0.16)
N3	264.05 (± 2.42)	63.09 (± 0.37)	-19.29 (± 0.36)
N4	250.02 (± 1.15)	64.43 (± 18.21)	-20.45 (± 16.82)
N5	247.04 (± 1.73)	61.77 (± 1.88)	-13.89 (± 1.79)
N6	239.03 (± 2.45)	52.8 (± 6.09)	-19.55 (± 5.71)
N7	193.04 (± 8.85)	51.44 (± 6.54)	-36.99 (± 19.89)
N8	173.03 (± 1.78)	45 (± 6.6)	-73 (± 11.71)

*we did not invert the geometry of this segment, since it is just a small connection between other segment. Only its slip distribution has been calculated.

Table S2. Rupture properties of each segment for both events (S1-14 for the strongest first event in the south while N1-8 for the second event in the north). Moment (and equivalent moment magnitude) was calculated for $\mu=3.3 \cdot 10^{10}$ N/m² as the sum of moments of each sub-source for each segment.

Segment	Length (km)	Width (km)	M0 ×E20	Mw	Slip (m) max/average / total	Stress Change (MPa) min/max	Stress Increase - Weighted Average [#] (MPa)	Stress Drop (MPa) Average* / Average** / Weighted Average***
S1	22	20	0.0206	6.14	1.1 / 0.8 / 15.6	-5.4 / 13.2	-1.13	5.3 / 9.4 / 7
S2	26		0.2860	6.90	4.5 / 2.7 / 216.6	-29.1 / 35.8	-3.86	10.3 / 14.6 / 11.9
S3	8		0.0913	6.57	9 / 0.3 / 69.2	-32.1 / 97.2	-11.03	30.6 / 62.7 / 43.5
S4	50		1.2500	7.33	14.7 / 6.7 / 943.8	-89.1 / 125.9	-15.15	23.6 / 54.4 / 31.5

S5	20		0.0454	6.37	4.8 / 2.5 / 34.4	-28.1 / 63.7	-5.01	11.5 / 40 / 24.1
S6	36		0.8070	7.20	9.3 / 5.7 / 611.5	-31.2 / 69.4	-9.79	17.9 / 23.5 / 20.7
S7	10		0.1260	6.66	8.1 / 5.5 / 95.7	-20.8 / 58	-4.49	24.2 / 48.9 / 29.6
S10	46		0.2140	6.82	9.2 / 4.3 / 161.8	-38.1 / 58.6	-5.35	14.5 / 38.6 / 23.3
S8	10		0.1410	6.70	8 / 5.5 / 106.9	-26 / 59.4	-10.00	16.3 / 27.5 / 18.8
S9	8		0.2790	6.89	6.4 / 4.6 / 211.1	-16.5 / 31.4	-8.16	13.8 / 20.8 / 16.3
S11	16		0.3090	6.92	9.6 / 6.4 / 233.9	-42.6 / 68.6	-12.68	23.6 / 36.1 / 28.9
S12	18		0.6030	7.12	12.7 / 5.6 / 456.8	-47.6 / 111.5	-4.63	15.3 / 41 / 26.6
S13	38		1.2800	7.34	6.9 / 4.3 / 972.6	-47.6 / 50.6	-6.93	13.3 / 20.7 / 16.2
S14	78		0.2790	6.89	7.4 / 4.3 / 211.6	-72.4 / 56.9	-10.25	8.7 / 14.9 / 11.5

N1	50	20	0.5380	7.08	8.1 / 3.9 / 407.9	-63.2 / 93.2	-9.58	17.8 / 31.6 / 25.2
N2	60		2.1800	7.49	15.1 / 7.3 / 1651.9	-72.8 / 150	-11.98	15.6 / 28.7 / 19.8
N3	16		0.3310	6.94	8.3 / 5.3 / 250.7	-57.2 / 82.8	-16.26	23 / 31.9 / 27.9
N4	6		0.1690	6.75	8.5 / 6 / 127.9	-50 / 42.6	-11.51	18 / 29.7 / 21.9
N5	10		0.1500	6.71	6 / 4.2 / 113.8	-11.2 / 33.1	-4.22	14.9 / 24.9 / 17.8
N6	6		0.0210	6.15	2.1 / 1.5 / 15.9	-5.1 / 15	-3.38	8.7 / 13.2 / 10.7
N7	10		0.0097	5.92	1.4 / 4.2 / 7.4	-11.2 / 33.1	-4.22	14.9 / 24.9 / 17.8
N8			0.1510	6.72	3.8 / 1.5 / 114.2			

#Average weighted by the slip amplitude and considering only sub-sources with negative stress change.

*Average considering only sub-sources with positive stress change.

**Average considering only sub-sources with stress drop and slip amplitude $>$ average slip on the fault.

***Average weighted by the slip amplitude and considering only sub-sources with positive stress change.